

Characteristic differences in the choice of factors of a healthy lifestyle as components of the individual physical culture of modern schoolchildren

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The article describes the factors of a healthy lifestyle, which adhere to schoolchildrens of different ages.

Purpose: *to explore the age-related features of the formation of the factors of a healthy lifestyle as components of individual physical education of schoolchildren of 11–17 years old.*

Material & Methods: *628 people took part in the study (282 young men; 346 women). In order to solve the research problems, a survey was conducted of respondents "Determining the motives and interests of schoolchildren in the field of physical culture and sports".*

Results: *it has been determined that motor activity, as one of the main factors of a healthy lifestyle in boys and girls aged 14–17, remains in the last place, except for sports class schoolchildrens. It is proved that only 34,1% of graduates, 48,9% of schoolchildrens in the 9th grade and 33,3% of ten schoolchildrens do not use alcoholic beverages. The highest percentage among smokers is in the 7th and 8th grades (33,3% and 22,7% respectively). Young men graduates are more likely to have a healthy lifestyle, and the percentage of those who smoke is reduced to 14,6%. Among the girls, it was found that 23,3% of ninth-graders smoke.*

Conclusion: *it is proved that in the age aspect there are quite significant differences between the boys and girls in choosing the priority factors of a healthy lifestyle, which they adhere to during the week. Attitudes towards bad habits are also different and ambiguous. That is, with age, the priorities of the value orientations of young people change, and the gender factor influences the formation of young men and women's views on maintaining a healthy lifestyle.*

Keywords: *schoolchildren, boys, girls, healthy lifestyle, physical education, sports, bad habits.*

Introduction

The deep socio-economic crisis that engulfed all sectors of the economy and the sphere of human life in Ukraine, military operations in the east of the country led to significant irreversible demographic losses.

According to the annual report on the state of health of the population, the sanitary-epidemic situation and the results of the Ukrainian health care system in 2016, alarming figures confirm that a significant part of the population of Ukraine leads an unhealthy lifestyle, in particular, the vast majority of Ukrainians are influenced by such risk factors as smoking, alcohol abuse, unhealthy diet, lack of physical activity and the like. Therefore, the preservation and strengthening of the health of the younger generation today is one of the urgent problems. The solution of this problem is of high social significance and is among the most important tasks of the state, since children's health is a fundamental basis for the formation of public health, the labor potential of the country and is a factor of national security [19].

This problematic has become especially actualized in the second half of the twentieth century both in the world as a whole and in Ukraine. The search for effective ways to form a healthy lifestyle is an interdisciplinary problem. WHO experts have determined the approximate ratio of various factors to ensure the health of modern man. It is believed that about 50% of health is determined by lifestyle – working conditions, habits, nutrition, moral and psychological stress, material and living

conditions, relationships in the family, etc. By 20% health depends on the genotype and 20% – on the state of the environment. And only 10% of health is due to the health system [22]. It is easy to understand that it is much more effective to form a healthy lifestyle, value-motivational settings on health than to change the genotype and environment - more conservative and stable components. Therefore, scientists point out that the image of his life is of great importance for the preservation of the health of the younger generation. But, unfortunately, the modern youth in the vast majority of cases do not think about their behavior, carelessly relate to their health, cultivate bad habits. It is known that almost 75% of adult diseases are obtained by them in childhood and adolescence. I. Vorontsov notes that the problem of the formation of the basis of a healthy lifestyle is especially relevant for schoolchildrens of school age, since during this period the development of its own program of life occurs, and the child is included in the complex work on the formation of self-reflection, self-control and self-regulation [5]. At the same time leading scientists [1–3; 6] the main factor of strengthening and preservation of health consider systematic motor activity, is formed in the process of physical education. The problem of the formation of a healthy lifestyle is sufficiently elucidated in many scientific works of modern scholars [8; 9; 13; 16; 22]. Scientists also proved that biological, sexual and psychological differences between boys and girls can, by correcting, influence the pupils' conscious attitude towards physical education and sports, and develop their healthy lifestyle habits [12; 15; 17; 20]. At the same time, the question of the characteristic differences in the choice of factors of a healthy lifestyle of

schoolchildren in the age aspect and sexual aspects was not the subject of special studies. Given the social significance and relevance of the problem, which involves the educational, recreational and general educational effect in the process of physical education, as a pledge of optimal intellectual, spiritual, social and physical development of schoolchildren, the relevance of this study is determined.

Purpose of the study: to explore the age-related features of the formation of the factors of a healthy lifestyle as components of individual physical education of schoolchildren of 11–17 years old.

Material and Methods of the research

The contingent of schoolchildren of 5–11 grades was investigated with an increase in the representativeness of the sample. The total number of respondents was 628 people (boys – 282; girls – 346). The results of the study stratified according to the age periods of the physiological development of children and biological sex. The reliability of differences between individual results is calculated at the level of reliability $p < 0,05$ to $p < 0,1$, which indicates the possibility of taking them into account when developing practical recommendations for physical culture teachers, as well as for further interpretations.

Results of the research

The attitude of a person to his own health is determined by many factors. From the place occupied by health in the value system of a young person, his attitude to a healthy lifestyle depends. A healthy lifestyle in the youth environment is becoming more meaningful. In the practice of physical culture, the following main factors of a healthy lifestyle are considered: motor activity, the absence of bad habits and healthy eating. Consider the attitude of young men and women to the value of

health through the lifestyle they lead. To determine the preferences of schoolchildren about the factors of a healthy lifestyle, which they adhere to during the week, we asked the question: "What factors of a healthy lifestyle do you follow during the week?". Respondents were given 5 answers: cold water hardening, personal hygiene, sleep, balanced eating, movement and bad habits (that is, their absence) (Tables 1, 2).

The results of the study determined that the children of the 5th and 6th grade (11–12 years old) arranged the factors of a healthy lifestyle as follows: first place - cold water hardening, second – personal hygiene, third – no bad habits and eating patterns (most likely, the guys noted the factors about which the teacher spoke, and not those that they adhere to (Table 1). The 7th grade youths in the priority factors are: the absence of bad habits, personal hygiene and motor regime.

In girls of the 5th and 6th grades, the priority is somewhat different factors of a healthy lifestyle: personal hygiene, sleep patterns, movement patterns and the absence of bad habits (Table 2). Analyzing the answers, it should be noted that among the boys and girls from the 9th to the 11th grades (14–17 years old) the factor "personal hygiene" was determined primarily among other factors of a healthy lifestyle. Then, according to the rating, the guys have no bad habits, the girls have a sleep mode and a meal mode. Unfortunately, the motor mode as one of the main factors of a healthy lifestyle among boys and girls 14–17 years old remains in last place, except for schoolchildrens of sports classes (in this category of respondents the motor mode takes second and third positions, entering the top three). On the absence of bad habits, then only girls of 14–15 years old, the main factor for themselves was determined by the "absence of bad habits".

The value attitude of schoolchildrens to their health is manifested in their method and lifestyle. The study stipulated that

Table 1
Factors of healthy lifestyle, which schoolchildren adhere to during the week (boys, points, rating)

Answer choices	5th class		6th class		7th class		8th class		9th class		10th class		11th class	
	$\bar{X}$	Rating	$\bar{X}$	Rating	$\bar{X}$	Rating								
Cold water hardening	3,00	1	2,70	1	3,93	5	3,68	4	3,88	2	4,58	6	4,24	1
Personal hygiene	3,00	2	3,22	2	3,47	3	3,32	2	2,98	6	2,83	1	2,24	6
Sleeping mode	3,67	4	4,13	6	4,33	6	3,59	3	4,31	1	3,25	3	3,80	3
Meal Mode	3,56	3	3,78	4	3,87	4	3,00	1	3,71	3	3,83	5	3,34	4
Motor mode	3,69	5	3,83	5	2,93	2	3,73	5	3,50	5	3,42	4	3,88	2
No bad habits	4,31	6	3,35	3	2,47	1	3,91	6	3,55	4	3,08	2	4,24	1

Table 2
Factors of healthy lifestyle, which schoolchildren adhere to during the week (girls, points, rating)

Answer choices	5th class		6th class		7th class		8th class		9th class		10th class		11th class	
	$\bar{X}$	Rating	$\bar{X}$	Rating	$\bar{X}$	Rating								
Cold water hardening	4,25	6	4,41	6	4,92	6	2,71	1	3,90	3	4,00	4	4,85	1
Personal hygiene	2,68	1	2,94	2	3,75	4	3,24	2	2,20	6	2,00	1	1,83	6
Sleeping mode	3,29	3	3,88	5	4,00	5	3,71	4	3,03	5	4,53	6	3,58	4
Meal Mode	3,79	4	3,76	4	3,50	3	3,86	6	3,33	4	3,47	3	3,65	3
Motor mode	3,79	5	3,59	3	2,75	2	3,71	4	4,00	2	4,27	5	3,71	2
No bad habits	3,21	2	2,41	1	2,08	1	3,38	3	4,17	1	2,53	2	4,85	1

the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the theory and practice of education should be most logical in the process of physical education of schoolchildren, since the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of a healthy lifestyle is one of the main tasks of physical education of the younger generation. In our opinion, due to the lack of relevant knowledge and attitudes, schoolchildren do not have well-defined associations with the concept of a "healthy lifestyle". This is confirmed by the fact that such an important factor in a healthy lifestyle as the motor mode was not determined by our respondents in the first place in the same age category of respondents.

Scientists note that the teenage period is considered a period of relatively good health. It is also the time of enormous changes in the physical, mental and social conditions, on the background of which the behavior consists, affects the health. The patterns of behavior that are formed in the early period of life are often preserved in adulthood. The most devastating impact on the health of adolescents today is the spread of harmful habits: smoking, alcohol, drugs and their consequences [4].

Consider bad habits in the life of schoolchildren (Figure 1, 2). The study found that the largest percentage of young people who smoke are in the 7th and 8th grades (33,3%, 22,7%, respectively). In the 11th grade, boys are more healthy and the percentage of smokers is reduced to 14,6%. We received alarming data on girls' smoking: 23,3% of ninth-graders smoke constantly, 33,3% of seventh-graders and 28,5% of 8th grade pupils know fashion and sometimes smoke. 25% of high school students previously abused, but subsequently quit smoking. It should be noted that, despite the proclaimed health-improving orientation of physical education, health did not become the main value of physical education in school.

Scientists argue that drinking alcohol is closely linked to the following typical behaviors of older adolescents: the reaction of emancipation and the reaction of grouping with peers.

Figure 1. Number of boys who smoke (%)

Figure 2. Number of girls who smoke (%)

Drinking can lead to serious and irreversible complications of health, such as brain disorders in adolescents, causing permanent memory problems, persistence of attention and reaction time, increased ability to damage the liver at an early age, hormonal imbalance, necessary for normal development of organs, muscles and bones – in particular, during puberty [4]. According to the results of our study, 13,33% of fifth-graders, 21,74% of 6th grade students, 33,33% of 7th grade students, 33,6% of eighth-graders gave a positive answer to the question about alcohol consumption among children and boys, 26,5% of 9th grade students, 58,3% of tenth-graders and 56,1% of graduates. Respondents noted that sometimes they drink alcohol on holidays. It was determined that only 34,1% of graduates (grade 11), 33,3% of tenth-graders, and 48,9% of 9th grade students do not drink alcoholic beverages. In addition, it has been found that quite a large percentage of girls use alcoholic beverages. It was shocked by the fact that already from the 7th grade, 66,6% of girls were drinking alcohol. Despite the above data, "the absence of bad habits" is in the priority responses to the choice of factors of healthy lifestyle in the 7th grade students. In the 11th grade – 77,7% of girls also noted that they sometimes drink alcohol.

Figure 3. Number of boys who drink alcohol (%)

Figure 4. Number of girls who drink alcohol (%)

According to the results of the questionnaire, two pentagrams and six young graduates are using drugs, among them three girls.

Scientists emphasize that the most important distinctive feature of the teenage period are fundamental changes in the field of self-awareness, which are of great importance for the further development and formation of adolescents as individ-

uals. According to one of the major domestic psychologists B. G. Ananyev, it was during this period that consciousness, having passed through most of the objects of relationships, itself becomes an object of self-awareness and, completing the character structure, ensures its integrity, promotes the formation and stabilization of the personality (B. G. Ananyev 1980, p. 89). Therefore, thanks to physical culture and sports, it is necessary to create such conditions that contribute to the formation of students' right attitude to health as a basic human value, which will significantly affect their reflective activity and awareness of personal responsibility for their own health. In addition, you need to teach schoolchildren to master the skills and abilities of a healthy lifestyle, to cultivate in them the need for physical improvement, shaping the values of physical culture and sports.

Conclusions / Discussion

Modern researchers propose to consider "Physical culture" at school as one of the leading disciplines of the curriculum, which aims at the formation of special knowledge, skills and abilities to use physical culture to ensure optimal functioning, physical and intellectual self-improvement. Scientists note the need to provide students with knowledge about the benefits of mastering motor skills and how to apply this knowledge [16]. Along with this, it is necessary to take into account that the specificity of physical education is that conscious information becomes a motivated incentive to perform physical exercises. The criterion of the effectiveness of the process should be the level of health of adolescents, the level of their physical performance and social viability (T. Yu. Krutsevich, 2012). So, based on the situation that exists today in the field of physical culture and sports, there is a problem of forming the value relationships of the younger generation to their health, healthy lifestyles, systematic physical activity through physical culture, that is, improving their natural inclinations for the realization in society, will increase not only personal achievements in their physical corporeality and the results of social activity, but will be a definite contribution to the development of the general culture of society.

Scientific interest was aroused in our studies by I. V. Evstigneev. In a scientific study "Gender education of primary school students in physical education classes," the scientist studied the pedagogical conditions of gender education in primary

school students in physical education classes in the university. The author has proven that the main criteria for gender education of primary school students in the process of physical education is cognitive, emotional-value, motivational and behavioral. Scientists have justified and experimentally verified pedagogical conditions aimed at taking into account the age and sex characteristics of children in primary school in physical education classes, the acquisition of knowledge in physical education classes about the essence of gender education; use of interactive teaching methods that promote adolescent gender education; creation of micro and macro environment, aimed at gender adaptation of students of primary school [7].

Also, in our opinion, the study of A. V. Zakin end is interesting: "Preparing future physical education teachers for raising healthy lifestyles for younger schoolchildren on the basis of a gender approach", in which the scientist defined the essence of a gender approach to raising healthy lifestyles for younger schoolchildren as organizing educational process, provides students with the opportunity for self-realization with their inherent individual characteristics and to assimilate social experience, ensures their successful socialization in society and social identification by the gender.

As a result of studying and theoretical analysis of sociological and psychological-pedagogical literature, analyzing the results of our research, which concerns the definition of differences in the choice of healthy lifestyle factors for schoolchildren of different age groups, it is proved that in the age aspect there are quite significant differences in the choice of priority factors of a healthy lifestyle, which they adhere to during the week. Attitudes towards bad habits are also different and ambiguous. That is, with age, the priorities of the value orientations of young people change, and the gender factor influences the formation of the ideas of young men and women on maintaining a healthy lifestyle. The study does not exhaust all the issues of the indicated problem. The research results open up prospects for studying issues related to the influence of physical culture and sports on the gender socialization of schoolchildren, the preparation of individual programs for the gender development of adolescents, and the development of pedagogical foundations for the organic combination of students' gender opportunities with their physical development and self-development.

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